

RELEVANCE AND RESPONSIVENESS OF MAED SCIENCE PROGRAM FOR THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF GRADUATES

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to describe Master of Arts in Education (MAEd) Science program in terms of objectives, student outcomes, teaching-learning activities and assessment tools. It also assessed the relevance and responsiveness of the program on the personal and professional growth and development of graduates. Furthermore, the problems met in the implementation of the program relative to curriculum and instruction were also identified. The descriptive method of research was utilized with the aid of the researcher-made questionnaire as the primary tool in gathering data. Composite mean and weighted mean were the statistical tools used in quantifying the gathered data. The study revealed that the program contributed to the overall quality of education by becoming professionally attuned to a wide range of effective educational practices. The students' outcomes focused on the use of appropriate technologies to communicate, collaborate, solve problems, make decisions and foster creativity and lifelong learning. The study also found that the teaching and learning activities provided by the program develop research skills by conducting action research and other research related activities. Students' performance was evaluated through individual reports by the used of the portfolio. Further, it was found out that the programs were relevant and responsive to the personal and professional development of graduates, particularly in dealing with other teachers and researchers and in developing literacy skills necessary in conducting research. Moreover, the program implementers encountered problems on monitoring of curricular related activities, platforms for collaborative works and instructions. From the findings, the program objectives, and student outcomes are attained, but further enhancement must be done in teaching and learning activities and assessment tools.

Keywords: Science program, relevance and responsiveness, descriptive, Philippines